

IMPROVED ALGORITHM FOR AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE SCREENING

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ABSTRACT

Although temperature cameras cannot be used to detect infection or the existence of viruses, temperature cameras can be used to detect elevated body temperatures. The FLIR temperature scanner has long been used in public places, such as airports, train terminals, business establishments, factories, and skin surface measurements, as an effective tool and Elevated Body Temperature (EBT) Is helpful in identifying individuals. Affected by the global outbreak of Corona virus disease (COVID-19), it has been officially identified as an epidemic. Society is deeply concerned about the spread of infection, and is eventually looking for tools to stop the spread of the virus. The FLIR camera can be used as a screening tool to detect the increased skin temperature in the highest traffic public places through rapid individual screening. If the skin temperature is found above the average temperature in major body locations, such as the corner of the eye, and forehead, then the individual may be selected for additional screening. It is necessary to identify individuals with EBT, who should then be sent to a virus-specific diagnostic testing center for examination. This may help in reducing the spread of viruses, and infections. All the methods available to measure body temperature are all based on edge detection. These methods are very sensitive to noise, and in these the system of noise reduction is quite complex. Therefore, an automated method is being introduced to measure the temperature of the corner of the Eye and Forehead using the "salt and pepper" and "colormap" method, which is less complex, and still has high accuracy.

Keywords: FLIR, Hyperthermia, DITI, EBT, SARS, Thermography.

I. INTRODUCTION

As is well known, cases of Covid-19 are increasing globally. We are using technology in such a way as to prevent the spread of the virus by monitoring the huge population. Major natural non-invasive techniques currently employed using supernatural thermal imaging handheld non-touch thermometers or pyrometers by detecting border invasions, and the thermal readings estimation. Ideally, the best use of the temperature image is with a certified reference black body source positioned in the invisible region. Handheld noncontact pyrometers are being installed to detect fever in a particular person. Estimation of thermal readings with an infrared radiation camera is also beneficial for patients as well as physicians. Thermography is patient-friendly as a non-contact and non-invasive diagnostic procedure. This not only helps in estimating prematurely rising temperatures, but also provides a complex image of evaluating patients' body temperature.

Thermography is a method, that is based on infrared radiation. An infrared camera is used in this method to isolate blood circulation in body tissues [11]. Information is extracted from body temperature reading assessments, through which many disease patterns can be diagnosed. Therefore, thermography represents a very obedient course unlike other proceedings in medical science, which are also highly prudent. Thermographic diagnosis is often related to body heat. In areas of healthy body, the involvement is balanced on emission of object temperature unlike a sick person [2]. Image processing is a comprehensive technique for diagnosing illness or a disruption in the human body, an important contribution to the education world. Today abnormal body temperature can be a sign of this disruption [10]. Digital Infrared Temperature Image (DITI) is an effective, and non-invasive tool to monitor temperature variation. Temperature variation between 36.30 centigrade to 37.50 centigrade is considered the norm, and going above it signifies signs of illness, commonly called temperature radiation [14].

II. THERMOGRAPHY

The need for rapid, and accurate determination of human body temperature is increasing, due to which highly capable, intelligent, and high-resolution temperature imaging camera systems are being developed to make a difference in temperature. Thermography is a process, that is used as a non-contact instrument to detect brightness differences in temperature. It is an easy and simple way to set up, and operate a non-contact system.

It helps to monitor, and identify the increase in surface temperature of the skin (usually the face, forehead, and corner of the eye), which is usually found in a person with a high fever [2].

Fig-1: A temperature imaging camera uses one to identify the temperature [13]

The temperature infrared camera is a device for converting infrared radiation to electrical output, as shown in figure 1. Grayscale may be helpful to the image prediction [14]. FLIR is one of the most reliable and preferred temperature images in medical research and studies and 320x240 pixels are used for optimal radiation resolution medical analysis in ideal conditions [3]. An output signal is obtained from the detector which can be very long, so amplification is required, but before that a filter has to be installed, which is weak and suitable for band width [11].

2.1 Background

Heat transfer can be described by three modes. The Stefan-Boltzmann law describes the determination of these transformations. The power of the temperature emitted by a black body can be calculated by equation (2), which is as follows [3]:

$$P = \epsilon \cdot S \cdot \sigma \cdot T^4 \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where,

$$\sigma = 5,6703 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{K}^{-4}$$

ϵ = Emissivity (0 & 1)

S = Surface

T = Temperature

III. MOTIVATION

Infrared temperature imagery is employed in medicine from 1960. There are many medical conditions, that are identified through changes in body temperature. The simple, and usual means of detecting fever in daily life is to find it by touching the body only. Determining the amount of fever is also necessary to understand the severity of the disease [15]. By using temperature cameras, authorities will be able to identify, and treat individuals in a more efficient, and effective manner, who will be sent for further screening for virus specific tests [13]. The primary objective of the proposed work is to improve the ability of temperature imaging as a useful tool to detect symptoms of Covid-19.

IV. LITERATURE

B. Jones et al. [2] has shown that a thermal image can be used to find blood vessels close to the surface of the skin with increased temperature. Its fundamental is the distribution interpretation of temperature in terms of physical changes with natural heat radiation emitted by the individual's skin. Spectral Radiant Flux $F_{e\lambda}$ is called power that is released, transferred, or acknowledged per interval wavelength as per radiation; Radiant flux F_e is integrated in the entire wavelength and its unit is watt.

$$F_e = \int_0^\infty F_{e\lambda} \cdot d\lambda \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

The value of the λ is from 380 to 780nm [2].

Eddie Y. K. Ng et al. [4] have suggested that the thermal imager can be used for large-scale blind screens when readings from a specific area correlate with ear temperature. They have done this test to differentiate between normal and febrile groups, and have experimented to obtain the optimal boundary temperature. An already usual threshold cutoff for thermal image is stated to be 36.30 centigrade, which is reference value. If a reading exceeds, the alarm will be off, as well as thermometer may be used for verification whether a person experiencing fever [4].

Manjula K A et al. [10] Defines 2 categories of methods used, which are analog & digital image processing [10]. In a human eye, there is a lack of response in absence of light in range 0.4µm - 0.7µm, so where light is low, the need for a device to produce the image by generating major energy [14]. Wavelength of intensity peak was described by Wien's displacement law as:

$$\lambda_{\max} = \frac{2.898 \times 10^{-3}}{T} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Experimental analysis has proved that thermography imaging techniques to assess temperature differences in the toes have helped in analyzing abnormally and efficiently [12].

4.1. Problem Formulation

Early imaging systems were difficult and complex with Bossini features for measuring performance and temperature. Computer image processing was done by thermograms in the 1970s, which increased the possibilities for the quantification and collection of images [1]. However, using infrared radiation systems for temperature screening offers a variety of advantages. In addition, its cost and method of measurement are many parameters that can affect its accuracy [13]. It is also very significant to know that, the temperature of the skin does not depend only on the body's temperature, but can also be precious from the work related to the environment, and other physical activities [4]. FLIR temperature cameras can be actively employed, especially for screening passengers at airports, screening for flight crew, and monitoring at railway stations, but there is a major problem, requiring a man to screen. Separate manpower has to be deployed to do this work. Due to this the general category is being affected.

V. PROPOSED WORK

Temperature inequalities are caused by differences in hormones or White Blood Cells (WBC), which help the body regulate the immunity of the human body. Temperature inequality is an abnormal growth inside the Throat. Detection of temperature variations in the initial phase is necessary to perform its successful treatment. The temperature distribution can be 37.50 centigrade or more if hyperthermia is obtained with the deviation of the temperature of the forehead and eye. When the temperature distribution is very low, it is called hypothermia. Both hyperthermia and hypothermia should be measured by the same method, so that the proposed method can work at all types of temperatures. Limited data have been published to identify fever, but a temperature of 380 centigrade or higher on the face is considered febrile [7].

Fig-2: Forehead and Eyelid Images of Human: (a) Forehead and Eyelid locations, (b) Thermal image shows even distribution heat, (c) Thermal Image shows uneven distribution of heat

When the temperature of Patient's ear-drum is 38 degrees centigrade and greater, it is immediately isolated for

further testing [5]. The only drawback of the system given by W. Chiu et al. is that, it has a false negative identity, and reduces the sensitivity of the fever probe [5]. This can happen, because the ear-drum was measured. If measurements were made on the forehead, and corner of the eye, the performance could have improved, as these locations are more sensitive in case of Covid-19. From the regression analysis, it is known that the best measurement should be done by taking the temperature in the corners of the eye. After that, temperature measurement can be taken in the forehead area [4].

Temperature imaging in medicine uses radiation emitted naturally from the surface of the skin. It works in the environment without any ambient light [2] [13]. Figure 2 (b) shows the normal distribution of heat under control. Figure 2 (c) shows the abnormal emission of heat in the reference area which can be classified as a "Temperature Abnormality". It also depends on other factors in various ways. If any object emits a temperature of zero Kelvin, it can be identified by electromagnetic radiation. The ambient temperatures are mainly inside IR band, which are then transformed into appropriate electrical signals using the appropriate detector, and are displayed on the monitor.

5.1 Proposed Model

The first is to capture the patient's image. Full description of the image can be obtained with the help of 'fullsize' instruction using MATLAB. The image will be found by Thermal Camera, it means that, it is RGB image. Now, all the pixels of the image will be manipulated. The larger the pixel matrix, the better the histogram will be found in the output. The value of 'numberOfColorChannels' is kept 3, because we are taking the RGB image here. Now the size of the image will be described. That is, we will define the matrix of pixels. To convert the 3D matrix to a 2D matrix, divide all pixels by 255. Because the 'colormap' value can be kept between 0 and 1 only [14]. 0 means dark pixel and 1 means light pixel.

5.2 Results and Discussions

Need to flip up / down because the low rows are the high temperatures, not the low temperatures. It is necessary to convert RGB image to Gray image to get more Accuracy. The running time of the existing algorithm for the Edge detection is considerably higher [8]. So, now we will create a Gray Index Image [8].

Now the value of low temperature i.e., 0.1oC and higher temperature will be 37.5oC, which is found in a healthy person. We will define these values.

$$\text{highTemp} = 37.5 \text{ and } \text{lowTemp} = 0.1$$

Fig-4: Temperature detection on the face of Female personnel

Now all the pixels of the Thermal Image will be measured, and create floating point thermal image. According to the temperature, a histogram of each pixel will be drawn, so that the frequency with high temperature can be detected. Now, put the boundary values for temperature. In the image obtained, the temperature can be obtained by color of each pixel by the movement of the mouse, as shown in Figure 5.

Fig-5: Temperature measurement and histogram of Female Face Image

If this frequency is too high then the probability of Hyperthermia being high will be high. If no temperature above 37.5°C is attained, it means that the normal temperature is present in the patient being measured. The theory behind facial thermography is that the disorder is arising and developing from high levels of blood. This disorder is caused by high demand for essential nutrients. Because the blood temperature is usually high, the tissues around it show the area in which there is more blood flow, the higher the temperature. An imager then converts thermal energy into electrical colors reflecting diverse temperatures. The unusual rise is the melody that something is wrong. However, it may not necessarily be the Hyperthermia symptom. But there is something that needs to be studied and analyzed further.

VI. CONCLUSION

The proposed work presents an overview of the literature on thermal image processing and techniques regarding the outcome and success for identifying temperature disparities in health care systems. Apart from this, information and identification of literary research and gaps in this work have also been provided. Research on thermal image techniques and algorithms has been collectively identified through existing studies and simulated using MATLAB R2020a. There is no need to deploy the proposed work, and everything can be done automatically. Whenever it comes to detecting potential infections, the first step is the screening process applied at airports and other public places. This is a side way to screen for anyone. Screening should always be followed before the authorities decide to monitor a person. Thermal images take longer to be screened, so in future we will try to measure temperature through video thermography to increase the speed of screening.

VII. REFERENCES

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